

“KOMMIKA” MATH AND PHYSICS COMIC APPLICATION AS A LEARNING MEDIA BASED ON ANDROID

**Wulansari¹, Roberto Abimanyu Baggio¹, M. Nurilman Baehaq¹,
Aisyah Denta Kusuma¹, Hani Harjayanti¹**

¹State University of Jakarta, Rawamangun Muka Street No 1, Jakarta 13220

wulansari9703@gmail.com

Abstract

Nowadays world is in industry revolution 4.0, it is a condition where technology information has become a base in human's life (Ristekdikti, 2018). One of development in industry is utilization comic as entertainment media visual by use gadget. Indonesian comic books association (AKSI) noted that 13 million people read Indonesian comics by their smartphone (Harian Nasional, 2018). However, the contents of these comics are still dominated with entertainment and few comics has educational content. Based on the result of preliminary research, we found that 95,7% students enjoy learning by using android application, 56,5% students stated that an alternative of learning media is the usage of android application, 78,3% students are interested in using android application as a learning media, and 73,9% students agreed to use android media as their learning media. On the other hand, based on the research, the most difficult lesson according to the student is math and physics. To compensate for these conditions, KOMMIKA (Komik Matematika dan Fisika) is created as a learning media based on android application which also contains knowledge of science linked to everyday life. KOMMIKA is a visual learning media based on android to minimize the challenges that students face when learning mathematics and physics.

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1. Introduction

Science has an important role in supporting human's life. Mathematics and physics are the branches of science which are often learned. These two lessons are related to each other. Many mathematical concepts used as physics solving techniques, such as vector calculation, speed, thermodynamics and others.

Mathematics and physics are a very important lessons to be taught to the student. In Indonesia, this is indicated by the existence of mathematics and physics lesson since elementary school. Physics that are learned in science lesson teach students how to understand physical phenomena in this world. In physics lesson student learn why the sun rises in the east, why is there day and night, why do things fall down when it thrown, why is there changes of objects after burning, and many more.

Such problems can be answered using a physical and mathematical approach. However, there are problems such as learning methods or media that are still conventional and often inhibit student in understanding these lessons. In mathematics, problems that often arise are students' reasoning ability, skills and understanding of teachers in carrying out learning process, students' awareness of learning, student with memory, language, or reasoning disorders, and feeling of fear from the student [1]. In Physics, in general the problem that arise are due to students' weakness in structured abilities especially the ability to use knowledge schemes in create problem solving strategies, misconception, mathematical abilities, and the ability to understand prerequisite knowledge.

Nowadays, world is in industrial revolution 4.0, that is the condition has been become a base in human's life. The development of the massive internet and digital technology makes things borderless with computing and unlimited data [2]. In the presence of industrial revolution 4.0, we need to use technology to solve problems in learning.

One of the solutions to overcome the problems in learning is using visual media in giving teaching to mathematics and physics lesson. Based on the results of research by Widyasari [3] that the gift of visual props in physics learning is more effective than without visual props. Many teenagers are currently using pictorial media like as Webtoon or Instagram.

Webtoon users in August 2017 reached over 6 million users [4]. Instagram besides being a place to upload personal photos, is now a comic platform like as shenscomics, tahilalats, Si Juki, and others. In July 2017, Instagram user reached 45 million users [5]. It shows that teenagers are now likely to us media pictorial in their days. After looking at this situation, the issue of mathematics and physics learning can be solved by using media pictorial in its learning, not only through conventional text books. For that, we innovate created an android app called KOMMIKA (Comic Math and Physics based on Digital Apps). KOMMIKA.NET is a digital-based visual learning media that is carefully packed with purpose of facilitating student in learning mathematics and physics lesson to improve student knowledge with the approach of daily life issues. Characters and storyline of the comic in KOMMIKA refers to understanding of the concept of mathematics and physics.

Tedjasapurta argues that comics are illustrated cartoon stories where the elements of the picture are more important than the story [6]. According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, comics are illustrated stories (in a magazine, newspaper, or in the form of books) which are generally easy to digest and funny [7]. Handayani stated that "comic is a visual communication media that has the power to convey information popularly and easily understood [8]. Based on the above opinions it can be concluded that comics are visual communication media in the form of illustrated cartoon stories that are generally easy to digest and funny and have the power to convey information in a popular and easy to understand manner.

Adi in Agatha explained the types of comics into several types, namely: cartoon/cartoon (cartoon), comic strip, comic book, comic annual, comic album, online comic, instructional book in comic format, series of illustrations (Storyboard), comic bookings (simple comic), and comic planning thoughts. However, the type of comic that will be developed is online comics [9].

According to Gagne in Barus and Suratno media are various types of components in the student environment that can stimulate them to study [10]. Whereas according to Briggs in Barus and Suratno media are all physical devices that can present messages stimulating students to study [11]. Barus and Suratno said that the media is a tool used in the teaching and learning process aims to facilitate the teacher in conveying the subject matter and make it easier for students to absorb, understand or master the subject matter they receive [12]. Based on the above opinion it can be concluded that the media is a physical tool in the student environment that is used for teaching and learning processes that can present messages in a way that stimulates students to learn so as to make it easier for teachers to convey the subject matter and facilitate students in absorbing, understanding or mastering the material he received .

According to the Large Dictionary, Indonesian visual language is something that can be seen with the sight (eye) [13]. Prihadi suggested that visual is a learning activity by observing and describing [14]. Royan suggested that visuals are people who prefer to use vision in receiving information [15]. Based on the above opinion it can be concluded that visual is an activity of learning or receiving information through vision by observing and describing something that can be seen with the sense of vision.

Visual media can be interpreted as a physical tool in the student environment that is used for teaching and learning processes that can present messages by stimulating students through vision

to learn by observing and describing something that can be seen by the visual senses making it easier for the teacher to convey the subject matter and facilitate students in absorbing, understanding or mastering the material they receive.

Duffy and Roehler in Lefudin suggested that learning is a system that aims to help the student learning process, which contains a series of events that are designed, arranged in such a way as to influence and support the occurrence student learning processes that are internal [16]. According to Sudjana in Darma, learning is every effort made intentionally by educators that causes participants to carry out learning activities [17]. Miarso in Siregar et al. Stated that learning is an educational effort that is carried out intentionally, with the objectives set before the process is carried out, and its implementation is controlled [18]. So, learning is an educational effort that is done intentionally with a predetermined goal to help students' learning processes that are designed and structured in such a way that it can support the occurrence of an internal learning process.

Eggen and Kauchak in Lefudin explained that there are six characteristics of effective learning, namely (1) students become active reviewers of the environment through observing, comparing, finding similarities and differences and forming concepts and generalizations based on similarities found, (2) the teacher provides material as focused thinking and interacting in the lesson, (3) student activities are fully based on assessment, (4) the teacher is actively involved in providing direction and guidance to students in analyzing information, (5) learning orientation of content mastery lessons and development of thinking skills, and (6) teachers use varied teaching techniques according to the goals and style of teacher teaching [19].

2. Objectives

KOMMIKA (Komik Matematika dan Fisika) is created as a learning media based on android application which also contains knowledge of science linked to everyday life. KOMMIKA is a visual learning media based on android to minimize the challenges that students face when learning mathematics and physics. This study was conducted for 8 month januari to August 2018 which focused on the design and program of the media at the Secretariat of the Young Research Group of the Jakarta State University. The method used in designing this application is type system development method waterfall. This method was chosen because the stages are systematic and easy to apply. This research method will be presented in a flow chart image. the existing steps can be seen in figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart

Need analysis is used to get information, models, specifications about the software that the client / user wants. Both parties between the client and the software maker are actively involved in this stage. The system design stage allocates system requirements both hardware and software with a variety of system architectures as a whole. Software design and depiction of basic system software and intelligence abstraction. At this stage of implementation, software design is realized as a series of programs or program units. Testing involves verifying that each unit meets its specifications. In the testing phase, individual units of programs or programs are combined and tested as a complete system to ascertain whether or not they meet the needs of the software. After testing, the software can be sent to the user. Testing is done by blackbox testing and counting with statistics Descriptive. One of the results of the descriptive analysis will bring up calculations that are valued between 0 to 10. The average calculation is then interpreted according to the following interval:

Table 1 Statistics Descriptive

Average value interval	Interpretation
$0 < \text{mean} < 3,3$	the application runs poorly
$3,4 < \text{mean} < 6,6$	the application runs pretty well
$6,7 < \text{mean} < 10$	the application runs very well

3. Result and Discussion

The research method used in the study uses the Waterfall, the first stage carried out in this method is the needs analysis in which the problem can be inferred from the interviewee. The resource person here is the sample that is the target of marketing. The results of the needs analysis showed that 95,7% students enjoy learning by using android application, 56,5% students stated that an alternative of learning media is the usage of android application, 78,3% students are interested in using android application as a learning media, and 73,9% students agreed to use android media

as their learning media from the problem already identified, then design is done for help development system. Problems that arise I will make the features the available in the application this. There are designs for this application.

Figure 2. Design Of User Interaction With The System

This application was created by using Android Studio software. This software was chosen because of it provides a lot of libraries which can make it easier making Android applications. Where as for making web, researchers use Codeigniter framework. Framework is framework in engineering codings so functions frequent programming it is not written again like equivalent form, login handling, base access data, and others. Codeigniter chosen because it's simple, MVC concept (Model View Controller), has a level security, its users many, and have tools elegant. Management database created using phpMyAdmin. The programming language the one used is PHP, Javascript, HTML, and Bootstrap. designing and build this application, needed some software that is AndroidStudio, Ganymotion, Sublime Text and Web Browser. Android Studio is used to build

Android based application. this software too provides a lot of libraries that can be used that can facilitate system development. Ganymotion is used as an Android or an application can run an Android program in the Windows operating system. Sublime Text is used as an editor PHP. Web programming language the browser is used for display HTML and PHP code.

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Figure 3. Display android studio work to create applications.

The Kommika Android application can be used for users with Android software with a minimum version of 2.3.5 (Gingerbread).

ii. Product Development

The media manufacturing stage is the realization stage of the system design, at this stage learning media is created using Android Studio and Corel Draw. use of corel draw for the manufacture of comic designs and user interfaces, corel draw is used because it can produce images in the form of HD which makes the user more comfortable with the appearance of the application while the android studio software is used for programming applications so that they can be used by the user. Android studio is used because there is a library that facilitates coding of android programs

Figure 4. Main View 2

Figure 5. Login Page

On the main display page there is information and general objectives of KOMMIKA that are intended for each user. This is so that users can understand first about KOMMIKA and its objectives before using the application.

Login Page is one of the main pages at KOMMIKA, on this page users are required to have an account in order to access KOMMIKA wherever and whenever. Users who do not have an account will be asked to create me by signing up and filling in the personal data including name, e-mail address, and password to be able to register. Users who have registered for meals will be able to log in by entering their e-mail and password

Figure 6. Home Page 1

Figure 7. Quiz

On the home page, there are various choices of facilities that can be used by users freely. Available facilities include math comics, physics comics, material summaries, and quizzes. On this page there is also information about the favorite comic titles telling users and information about the top comics based on the number of readers.

Quiz page is intended for users who want to know the level of their understanding of the mathematical and physical concepts that have been obtained previously through comics and material summaries. On this page there is a score that provides information that the user's answer is right or wrong

Figure 8. List Of Comic

Figure 9. Example Comic

Comics are the main facilities found in KOMMIKA, there are 2 choices of material offered, namely mathematics and physics where in each material there are various titles that users can access freely. The storyline in the comics found in KOMMIKA is based on local culture and everyday life related to mathematics and physics, so readers can easily understand the basic concepts of physics and mathematics. Testing of the KOMMIKA.NET application is done using black box testing. The instrument and the testing results are as follows:

Table 2. Blackbox Testing Result

No.	Feature/action	expected results	test results
1	Register/sign up	after users input their data like name, school, born date, etc., then clicking 'Daftar' (Register), the data is stored in the database.	1
2	login to the server	After users input username and password, the apps shown its main page.	1
3	choose the subject categories	The list of comics appear.	1
4	choose the comic title	The comic appears according to what user has choosen.	1
5	click the 'like' button	The apps stores data into SQLite.	0
Total			4
Percentage			80%

Based on the table , it is found that most of the feature in this application can already be used with an 80% success rate. It shows that all function can be used properly.

4. Conclusion

The problem raised in the writing of this research is how to design and build KOMMIKA applications as visual media for learning Mathematics and Physics. The system development method used is methodology that consists of requirements gathering, planning, coding, and testing. The results of the development of this system is the creation of an KOMMIKA application based on Android with features such as class selection, reading, enjoying, and viewing subtitles. Stages of application starts from problem identification, design making base with phpMyAdmin, making interface display with Android Studio help, and creating logical business using Java programming language. After testing with the blackboxtesting method, the KOMMIKA application can be used by its functions with a success rate of 80%.

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